

School-level factors influencing NEET outcomes in England

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Summary

This study examines how school characteristics influence the proportion of students becoming NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training), addressing a gap in research by exploring school-level influences rather than individual (student-level) risk factors. Analysis of data from around 3,000 secondary schools in England suggest that even once variations in the pupil population and local economic context are controlled for, the way schools approach behaviour management, how well they support low-attaining student to progress, and whether they provide education up to the age of 18 can significantly influence the proportion of students who drop out within six months of graduating.

Keywords: Not in Education Employment or Training; NEET; school characteristics; risk factors; education outcomes; school inclusion

1. Introduction

From 2013, educational policies in England have mandated participation in education, training, or employment until the age of 18. Despite this, approximately 5% of 16–17-year-olds and 14% of 18-year-olds remain NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training; Department for Education, 2024). This status has been associated with a range of negative outcomes, including unemployment, lower wages, poor health, drug misuse and participation in criminal activity (Audit Commission, 2010; Crawford et al., 2011; Ralston et al., 2022). High rates of young people becoming NEET also have negative consequences for wider society and the national economy through demands on public services and financial support (UCL Institute of Health Equity, 2014).

This study forms part of a wider project to investigate the factors that compound or mitigate the risk of young people becoming NEET after they leave statutory schooling. Risk factors specific to individual students are well known, and include low socio-economic status (Bynner and Parsons, 2002; Duckworth and Schoon, 2012; Crowley et al., 2023), low attainment (Rahmani and Groot, 2023) and having special educational needs (Powell, 2021; Crowley et al., 2023).

However, despite considerable between-school variation in the proportion of students becoming NEET, limited attention has been paid to the role of school-level factors in NEET risk. This study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating how characteristics of schools – including their performance, staffing ratios, behaviour management approaches, and structural characteristics – influence the proportion of students dropping out within six months of graduating.

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2. Methods and Data

The study integrates data from multiple publicly available datasets, including school characteristics and performance metrics for three academic years (2021/22 to 2023/24) published by the Department for Education, and the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) assigned to each school's Lower Layer Super Output Area (LSOA) in 2019.

The following indicators were examined for ~3,000 mainstream secondary schools in England:

- **NEET Outcome:** Percentage of students not sustaining post-16 pathways ('not sustained' rate) per school.
- **School Characteristics:** Suspension rates, headcount, performance metrics, staffing ratios, identity (religious denomination, single-sex) and whether post-16 education is provided.
- **Control Variables - Pupil population:** Student demographics, eligibility for additional support, attainment metrics and absence rates as overall indicators at the whole school level.
- **Control Variables - Geographic and economic factors:** IMD of school LSOA, urban/rural classification

Linear regression models were used to assess the proportion of variation in 'not sustained' rates explained by each of the school characteristics, and the extent to which these relationships remained once controlling for characteristics of each school's overall student population and geographic and economic factors outside of the school's control.

A good model fit was determined based on the data for the 22/23 academic year, and then the selected model was applied to the remaining two years with no further tuning to protect against over-fitting. In each model, predictors (school characteristics) were entered first, and then controls were added.

Variables underwent transformation using the Python package 'sklearn.preprocessing' to better align with the assumptions of an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model. Binary indicators were encoded as nominal variables using 'OneHotEncoder', while Ofsted rating and IMD were encoded as ordinal variables using 'OrdinalEncoder'. A polynomial term was included for attainment indicators and headcount using 'PolynomialFeatures'. The remaining continuous variables, including the dependent variable were normalised using 'PowerTransformer'.

To explore whether the model prediction errors varied systematically by location, Moran's I was calculated, and spatial patterns were visualised by mapping model residuals across England at the school, local authority and region levels.

3. Results

School characteristics alone explained between 44 and 46% of the variance in school level 'not sustained' rates. The same significant relationships were observed across the three years (see **Table 1**) with pupil:teacher ratios, Progress 8 scores, faith schools and single-sex school being associated with decreased rates and assistant:teacher ratios, suspension rates and no post-16 provision associated with increased rates. School size (headcount) and Ofsted rating were not significantly related to 'not sustained' rates.

Once control variables were added to the models, the staffing ratio variables were no longer significant, but all other observed relationships between school characteristics and the outcome measure were preserved. Most of the control variables had the expected relationships with 'not sustained' rates, however the attainment indicators were not significantly related to the outcome measure.

Models containing the control variables had major issues with multicollinearity (see condition numbers in **Table 1**) despite explaining a larger proportion of variance in the 'not sustained' rates. This collinearity was primarily due to the relationships between the attainment indicators and these variables were subsequently removed from the models as they were not consistently significant.

Table 1 Variable regression coefficients and significance in OLS regression models explaining variation in ‘not sustained’ rates across three academic years.

Consensus between models is highlighted where applicable. R^2 indicates the proportion (between 0 and 1) of variance in the ‘not sustained’ rates explained by the model; The AIC score is used to compare fit between models – lower values are better; and high condition numbers (>100) indicate severe multicollinearity.

	Regression coefficients									Relationship to 'Not sustained' rates - Consensus
	2021-22 (N=2,844)			2022-23 (N=2,972)			2023-24 (N=3,019)			
	Predictors	Predictors and controls	Final model	Predictors	Predictors and controls	Final model	Predictors	Predictors and controls	Final model	
School characteristics										
Headcount	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000		NA
Headcount ²	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000		NA
Pupil:Teacher ratio	-0.080***	0.026*	0.021	-0.091***	-0.004	-0.005	Not available			NA
Assistant:teacher ratio	0.125***	0.003	0.023	0.092***	-0.005	0.015	Not available			NA
Suspension rate	0.277***	0.051**	0.067***	0.277***	0.054**	0.074***	0.283***	0.090***	0.117***	Increased rates
Progress 8	-0.503***	-0.801***	-0.178***	-0.525***	-0.463**	-0.106**	-0.595***	-0.768***	-0.205***	Decreased rates
Progress 8 ²	-0.076**	-0.149***	-0.013	0.039	-0.062	0.030	-0.024	0.024	0.037	NA
No Post-16	0.233***	0.191***	0.207***	0.234***	0.209***	0.214***	0.312***	0.224***	0.241***	Increased rates
Ofsted rating	-0.013	-0.018	-0.016	-0.025	-0.014	-0.014	-0.007	0.004	0.003	NA
Faith school	-0.175***	-0.138***	-0.141***	-0.147***	-0.112***	-0.123***	-0.071*	-0.078*	-0.111***	Decreased rates
Single sex school	-0.421***	-0.222***	-0.241***	-0.454***	-0.262***	-0.309***	-0.393***	-0.148**	-0.204***	Decreased rates
Controls										
Attainment 8		-0.055			-0.030			0.044		NA
Attainment 8 ²		0.001***			0.001**			0.000		NA
Absence rate		0.020	0.064**		0.053**	0.107***	Not available			Increased rates
Selective school		-0.403**	-0.392***		-0.345**	-0.248***		-0.400**	-0.371***	Decreased rates
Boys %		0.025*	0.026*		0.032**	0.038**		0.023*	0.029*	Increased rates
FSM %		0.393***	0.464***		0.351***	0.422***		0.368***	0.465***	Increased rates
SEN support %		0.008	0.036*		0.028	0.053***		0.025	0.055***	Increased rates
White British %		0.165***	0.150***		0.168***	0.149***		0.171*	0.159***	Increased rates
KS2 score		0.724			-0.498			-1.141*		NA
KS2 score ²		-0.004*			0.002			0.005		NA
IMD of LSOA		-0.016**	-0.016**		-0.019***	-0.020***		-0.012*	-0.013*	Decreased rates
Rural school		-0.117**	-0.087*		0.161***	-0.131***		-0.157***	-0.130***	Decreased rates
Summary statistics										
R ²	0.436	0.598	0.581	0.454	0.611	0.591	0.458	0.634	0.610	
AIC	6,536	5,668	5,738	6,729	5,819	5,922	6,800	5,700	5,849	
Condition No.	12,100,000	2,950,000,000	34	12,500,000	3,150,000,000	34	12,300,000	3,860,000,000	33	

¹ * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.00

The final models across the three academic years explained between 58 and 61% of the variance in ‘not sustained’ rates, and were in total agreement on the five school characteristics significantly associated with lower ‘not sustained’ rates (low suspension rates, high Progress 8 scores, post-16 provision, single-sex and faith schools).

Moran’s I highlighted a small but significant positive spatial autocorrelation (0.15, $p=0.001$) meaning schools tend to be similar to other schools nearby. Mapping residuals revealed slight geographic clustering of prediction errors (**Figure 1**). Subtle underestimations in Southeast England and overestimations in London suggest regional variations linked to NEET outcomes. Immediate future work will begin to explore the spatial dimensions of NEET explicitly.

Figure 1 OLS model residuals show small systematic errors in predicted ‘not sustained’ rates by geographic location

4. Discussion

Our findings corroborate previous research showing that high levels of deprivation among the student population and in the local area are significantly associated with higher proportions of students becoming NEET. Our study also confirms previous reports that White British ethnicity and eligibility for SEN support are associated with higher drop-out rates.

Contrary to previous research (Rahmani and Groot, 2023), neither primary nor secondary school attainment were consistently associated with ‘not sustained’ rates. These findings are particularly interesting given the emphasis traditionally placed on academic attainment and lend support to the recent inclusion of value-added metrics that recognise schools for investing in the progress of lower-attaining students.

Once controlling for individual and contextual factors, the most consistently significant school characteristics were:

- Suspension rate (the average number of suspension sessions per student in a school)
- Progress 8 score (the average student progress between key-stage 2 and key-stage 4 assessments)
- Religious denomination
- Single-sex schools
- Post-16 provision

Higher suspension rates and lower Progress 8 scores were associated with higher ‘not sustained’ rates. These indicators have been shown to reflect the inclusivity of a school’s culture, in terms of how behaviour is perceived and managed by teaching staff (Vavrus and Cole, 2002), and how much resource is invested in ensuring students at all levels progress (Day et al., 2016; Bernhard, 2020; Bernhard et al., 2024).

Single-sex and religious schools were significantly associated with lower ‘not sustained’ rates. This may be because such schools increase the similarity between students, and in the case of religious schools, between staff and parents. Increased similarity is associated with higher levels of school belonging and engagement in education (Finn and Voelkl, 1993; Casson, 2018).

Schools that offered post-16 provision tended to have lower ‘not sustained’ rates than those that did not. Prior qualitative research has highlighted a lack of information and guidance around post-16 pathways and the resulting indecision about next steps as an important reason young people give for becoming NEET (Siraj et al., 2014; Lőrinc et al., 2020). The option to remain in the same school for further education may help to mitigate this by providing a ‘default’ pathway for students to take.

The level of deprivation in the local area, as indicated by the IMD decile, was positively associated with ‘not sustained’ rates, even in the presence of a student population deprivation indicator (eligibility for free school meals). Plotting the residual errors from the model across a map of England indicates there may be some additional unmeasured factors influencing NEET rates at the Local Authority and regional levels. This finding illustrates how spatial analyses can complement traditional statistical approaches to uncover nuanced patterns in outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This research highlights the importance of the school environment in shaping students’ sustained participation in education, employment and training once they leave secondary school. This is especially important as the role of the school environment has historically been overlooked. Even once established individual and economic risks are controlled for, the approach schools take to managing behaviour, ensuring low performing students’ progress alongside their peers and whether education is offered post-16, significantly relate to the proportion of students who become NEET.

These findings reinforce the importance of considering contextual factors, including characteristics of the school learning environment, to provide a more holistic view of student-level NEET risk. They also have the potential to shape policy development around behaviour and inclusion in schools and may indicate a strength of providing all-through education to bridge the transition into post-16 provision.

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Biographies

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Nick Malleson is a Professor of Spatial Science and Cluster Leader for the Institute for Spatial Data Science (ISDS) at the School of Geography, University of Leeds. His research leverages techniques developed in computer science, statistics, and machine learning, applying them to critical social problems with a strong geographical context.